

SHORT COMMUNICATION article

Phytochemical study and proximate analysis of Libyan date seed cultivated in Al-Wahat Jalo oases

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Abstract: Date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera L.*) seeds, often regarded as agricultural byproducts, have recently garnered scientific interest due to their rich profile of bioactive compounds. In this study, Libyan date seeds from three cultivars (Saidi, Hamarai, and Degla) were analyzed to evaluate their physicochemical properties, including moisture, protein, ash, and phytochemical constituents. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of tannins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, saponins, coumarins, fixed oil, and steroids across all cultivars, though alkaloids were notably absent. Proximate analysis demonstrated distinct compositional differences: Saidi seeds exhibited the highest protein (6.7%) and lowest moisture content (5.9%), whereas, Hamarai seeds recorded the lowest protein (5.5%) and highest moisture content (8.6%). Degla seeds displayed intermediate values (5.6% protein, and 7.4% moisture). All cultivars shared identical ash content. These findings underscore the potential of Libyan date palm seeds as sustainable sources of natural therapeutic agents and nutritional supplements.

Introduction

The date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera L.*) is a member of the family Arceceae, also known as Palmaceae. It is widely cultivated in the Middle East and North Africa and holds significant cultural, economic, and religious importance. As a vital crop, its fruits, known as dates, are consumed globally by millions of people. Dates are particularly cherished for their cultural and religious significance, especially during the holy month of Ramadan, when Muslims traditionally break their fasts with them. The date palm, therefore, not only serves as a source of sustenance but also as a symbol of heritage and faith [1, 2].

Date seeds, often considered a byproduct of date fruit consumption, have recently, gotten the researcher's attention due to their potential phytochemicals, and nutritional, and functional properties. Date seeds are particularly distinguished by their high concentration of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and tannins [3-5]. These phytochemicals are responsible for their potent therapeutic application as antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory [6, 7]. In addition to these bioactive compounds, date seeds contain other phytochemical constituents such as fatty acids (oleic, lauric, palmitic, myristic, linoleic, and stearic acids) [8, 9], sterols, saponins,

and alkaloids, which further amplify their therapeutic potential [7, 10]. Further, date seeds are rich in essential nutritional components, including proteins, lipids, and minerals such as potassium, magnesium, and calcium. This diverse nutritional profile positions date seeds as a promising candidate for functional food applications [11-13]. Proximate analysis serves as a critical parameter for assessing the nutritional quality and richness of date seeds. Their biochemical profile is further analyzed to explore the potential applications of these byproducts, which are otherwise regarded as agricultural waste. However, there remains a notable lack of data on date byproduct investigations, particularly, mainly cultivars grown in diverse Libyan oases. This study aims to address this gap by characterizing seeds from selected Libyan date varieties to evaluate their compositional and functional properties.

Materials and methods

Seeds collection: Samples of date (fruits) at the Tmar stage which were locally known as Saidi, Degla, Hamarai, were originally collected in October 2023 from Al-Wahat Jalo oases, in the Al Wahat district in northeastern Libya. The date was identified by the local farmers whose expertise in morphological classification is honed through generations of selective cultivation. The dates were deseeded by removing the seeds and kept in a dry clean place.

Proximate analysis: One gram of each type of date seeds ground powder was weighed and dried at $105 \pm 2.0^\circ\text{C}$ for three hours to get the constant weight, cooled in a desiccator, and then weighed. The percentage loss in weight was expressed as the percentage of moisture content [14].

Protein content: The content was estimated by using the Kjeldahl method, where one gram (powdered) of each date seed sample was digested with 25.0 ml of sulfuric acid. The mixture was distilled into a boric acid solution (4.0%, w/v), then titrated with a hydrochloric acid solution (0.25 N). About two grams (powdered) of each sample, placed in a porcelain container, was ignited and incinerated in a muffle furnace at 550°C for four hours, the residue was expressed as a percentage [15].

Phytochemical analysis: Dates samples (1.0 Kg of each type) were pitted to remove seeds, followed by sun-dried for one week during summer time then heated in an oven at 105°C for three hours then roasted and ground into powder. The samples were subjected to extraction for phytochemical analysis using the specific test to identify the active constituent of each type of date seed sample in the current study [16, 17], and a methanolic extract was prepared to achieve the highest fixed oil content from the three seed cultivars.

Results and discussion

The date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera L.*) exhibits significant variation in its physical and chemical properties, influenced by geographical region, environmental conditions, and local climate. Libya, a vast nation with diverse climates, demonstrates this phenomenon distinctly. Along its Mediterranean coastline, characterized by mild, temperate weather, soft-textured dates are predominantly cultivated. In contrast, the central and southeastern oases, marked by harsher climates, yield semi-soft date varieties. Meanwhile, the hot, arid southern regions are renowned for producing dry Tamr, a firm, shelf-stable date type adapted to the extreme desert environment. This regional differentiation underscores how Libya's climatic diversity shapes the unique characteristics of its date palm cultivars [18, 19]. This study focused on three semi-soft date cultivars (Saidi, Degla, and Hamarai) cultivated in the Al-Wahat Jalo oasis region of Libya. Seed samples from these varieties underwent proximate analysis to evaluate their nutritional composition and physicochemical properties, **Table 1**. The findings of the current study,

indicate that date seeds account for approximately 7.0-14.0% of the total fruit weight. Among the evaluated cultivars, Saidi exhibited the highest average seed length (2.50 ± 0.10 cm), followed by Degla (2.37 ± 0.15 cm), though Degla displayed the smallest overall diameters. In terms of weight, Saidi recorded the highest seed mass (1.70 ± 0.208 gm), with Hamarai ranking second (0.82 ± 0.140 gm) as shown in **Table 1**. These results highlight distinct physical variations between the semi-soft date cultivars studied. These results were similar to those recorded by Libyan study for the same cultivars [19].

Table 1: Physical characters of seeds which represent three cultivars grow in Al-Wahat Jalo oases

Date cultivars	Length cm	Diameter cm	Weight gm
Saidi	2.50 ± 0.100	1.06 ± 0.061	1.70 ± 0.208
Degla	2.37 ± 0.150	0.83 ± 0.058	0.76 ± 0.023
Hamarai	1.87 ± 0.057	1.03 ± 0.057	0.82 ± 0.140

Proximate analysis of the three studied cultivars in **Table 2** revealed distinct differences in composition. Hamarai exhibited the highest moisture content ($8.6\pm 0.7\%$), followed by Degla ($7.4\pm 0.2\%$), with Saidi showing the lowest ($5.9\pm 0.1\%$). In contrast, Saidi demonstrated the highest protein content ($6.7\pm 0.3\%$), while Degla and Hamarai displayed nearly identical protein levels. Notably, all three cultivars shared comparable ash content ($0.8\pm 0.1\%$), indicating uniformity in mineral composition across the samples. Previous studies have suggested that variations in seed moisture content may correlate with climatic differences across the geographical origins of cultivars. However, in the current study, despite all samples being sourced from the same region, a difference in moisture content was observed, with the Saidi cultivar displaying the lowest levels compared to Hamarai and Degla. Notably, these findings of moisture, protein, and ash content still align with the moisture content ranges documented in earlier studies on Libyan date varieties [20, 21], and the same Moroccan, Emirates types [15, 22, 23] while based on moisture value, they slightly lower than Algerian types [24].

Table 2: Chemical composition of date seed cultivars

Date cultivars	Moisture content %	Protein %	Ash%
Saidi	5.9 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.3	0.8 ± 0.1
Degla	7.4 ± 0.2	5.6 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.2
Hemarai	8.6 ± 0.7	5.5 ± 0.2 %	0.8 ± 0.1

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the seed samples revealed a rich profile of bioactive compounds with potential therapeutic relevance. All three cultivars (Saidi, Degla, and Hamarai) tested positive for steroids, tannins, saponins, coumarins, flavonoids, and carbohydrates, though alkaloids were absent in all samples (**Table 3**). Notably, methanolic extracts demonstrated variable fixed oil content across cultivars: detectable levels were observed in Degla and Hamarai, while Saidi exhibited a significantly higher concentration. These findings underscore the seeds' diverse phytochemical composition, which aligns with their potential applications in natural product development and pharmacological research. The phytochemical profiles of the analyzed date seed cultivars revealed consistent trends: all samples showed no detectable alkaloids but tested positive for tannins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, coumarins, and fixed oils [5, 11]. Notably, the three Libyan cultivars examined in this study Saidi, Hamarai, and Degla unexpectedly exhibited positive results for steroids. This finding aligns with reports from date seed studies in Indonesia and Nigeria, suggesting a potential cross-regional similarity in steroid occurrence despite differing climatic or geographical origins and positive alkaloid content [4, 25].

Table 3: The findings of phytochemical screening of date seeds

Phytochemicals	Saidi	Degla	Hemarai
Steroid	+	+	+
Tannins	+	+	+
Fixed oil	+++*	+	+
Saponins	+	+	+
Coumarins	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+
Alkaloids	-	-	-
Carbohydrates	+	+	+

* An excessive amount of fixed oil was observed in the Saidi cultivar compared to the others

Conclusion: This study marks the comprehensive investigation into the phytochemical composition and proximate analysis of seeds from three date cultivars in Libya. The notable phytochemical and protein content observed in these seeds suggests their potential as valuable sources of natural therapeutic agents and nutritional supplements.

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